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Axial compression testing of carbon fibers

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Outline

1. General Introduction

2. Test Method

3. Results and Discussion

1. General Introduction

The development of fiber with higher strength has become the trends of carbon fiber technology in the world.

United States and Japan have developed a new ultra-high strength carbon fiber (IM10/T1100G)

1. General Introduction

The tensile strength of **Carbon fiber reinforced plastics** was increased by **fiber fining**, but the compressive strength was not increased.

The improvement of axial compression strength of CFRP requires promoting compression strength of carbon fibers .

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1. General Introduction

- ◆ Measurements of the axial compression strength of carbon fibers are much difficult than the tensile strength.
- ◆ There have been developed several methods for determining single fiber axial compression strength such as loop test tensile recoil test and direct single fiber test.
- ◆ However, the test dates of these methods are much lower than expectation.

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1. General Introduction

- ◆ In this study, the axial compression strength of carbon fiber multifilament has been determined on a series PAN-based carbon fibers using **bundle compression test** similar to the compression measurement of unidirectional laminated composites.
- ◆ This test allows for **rapid response and utilizes smaller amounts** of material for initial screening testing.

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2. Test Method

Tow compression specimen consists of an impregnated bundle carbon fibers surrounded by a resin tab.

2. Test Method

The compression specimen is placed into a mold, which also acts as the test fixture. Apply the force to the fixture at the specified rate until failure while recording data.

Fig.2. Schematic of fixture setup

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2. Test Method

Calculate the ultimate compression strength using equations 1.

$$F=P/A \quad (1)$$

Where:

F = compression strength, MPa,

P = failure force, N,

A = cross-sectional area at fiber section, mm².

The cross-sectional area at fiber section is calculated using equations 2

$$A=l/\rho \quad (2)$$

Where:

l = linear density, g/m,

ρ = fiber density, g/cm³.

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The axial compression strength was much lower than the tensile strength. It is also seen that the coefficient of variation of compression strength was higher than the tensile strength.

Tab.1 Axial compression strength values in PAN-based carbon fibers

Fiber grade	Yield /K	Compression strength /MPa	Tensile strength /MPa
T300B	6	2260(6.2)*	3655(3.2)
T700S	12	2523(7.8)	5180(2.8)
T800H	12	2835(5.0)	5630(2.5)
T800S	24	2229(6.6)	5910(3.6)
T1000	12	2462(6.2)	6410(2.7)
M40J	6	2431(4.5)	4502(3.5)
M55J	6	1886(6.8)	4062(4.2)

*Coefficient of variation (%) in parentheses.

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3. Results and Discussion

The compression section of the specimen presented shear failure morphology with an angle. For these carbon fibers, **kink bands appeared on the surface** as shown in Fig.3. The kink bands usually developed into splitting failure along the specimen axis.

Fig.3 Failure mode of multifilament specimen

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